

CAPTURING AND RANKING PERSPECTIVES ON THE CONSONANCE AND DISSONANCE OF DYADS

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ABSTRACT

In many domains we wish to gain further insight into the subjective preferences of an individual. The problem with subjective preferences is that individuals are not necessarily coherent in their responses. Often, a simple linear ranking is either not possible, or may not accurately reflect the true preferences or behaviour of the individual. The phenomenon of consonance is heavily subjective and individuals often report to perceive different levels on consonance, or indeed dissonance.

In this paper we present a thorough analysis of previous studies on the perception of consonance and dissonance of dyads. We outline a system which ranks musical intervals in terms of consonance based on pairwise comparison and we compare results obtained using the proposed system with the results of previous studies. Finally we propose future work to improve the implementation and design of the system.

Our proposed approach is robust enough to handle incoherences in subjects’ responses; preventing the formation of circular rankings while maintaining the ability to express these rankings — an important factor for future work. We achieve this by representing the data gathered on a directed graph. Abstract objects are represented as nodes, and a subject’s preference across any two objects is represented as a directed edge between the two corresponding nodes. We can then make use of the transitive nature of human preferences to build a ranking — or partial ranking — of objects with a minimum of pairwise comparisons.

1. INTRODUCTION

Subjectivity and the potential incoherency associated with it can be difficult to handle. Areas like psychology, sociology, aesthetics, music and computer science — collaborative filtering and recommender systems in particular — rely on the responses of individuals within a population who may or may not be expressing incoherent behaviour.

Another issue faced when dealing with human feedback is incomplete data. Often, the attention span of a subject is simply not long enough to collect sufficient information with incoherences potentially increasing over time. Some

studies disregard responses from subjects where inconsistencies in responses grow too large. In one example case, discussed further in section 2.2, sample sizes were reduced by almost half [1].

Using directed graphs to rank or sort objects is not a new idea. There are numerous topological sorting, or “toposort”, implementations using directed graphs. Topological sorting is achieved either by performing a reverse postorder depth first sort, or by pushing the first node found with no incoming edges onto a stack — the output — removing that node from the graph and repeating the process until all nodes have been stacked [2–5]. These approaches, however, rely on the graph to be acyclic, which is not typically guaranteed when dealing with subjective responses.

The field of graph theory is extensive, providing many tools for the representation, transformation and computation of digraphs. Further approaches within this domain have been described to rank players in a tournament [6] or candidates in an election using digraphs (both weighted and unweighted) [7, 8]. These approaches, while capable of handling cycles within the graphs, are restricted to semi-complete digraphs — digraphs where every two vertices are connected by at least one edge.

While these approaches may not be useful to us in most cases, some aspects, such as the Copeland score method [7] — see 2.4 — have been useful as a basis to form our own algorithms.

1.1 Motivations

In this paper we firstly present a review of previous studies in the area of consonance and dissonance of dyads. We then briefly identify an algorithmic approach to handle subjectivity using a digraph which addresses some of the issues faced by previous studies. The results obtained using this approach are then compared to the results of previous studies.

Our approach aims to be efficient in reducing the number of questions asked to each subject during a trial. Not only does this speed up the testing process but it also reduces the potential for incoherences which may increase over time.

Our approach also aims to be expressive enough to represent possibly contradictory answers from subjects. We believe this incoherence may prove to be useful information in terms of accurately describing the preferences of an individual. The expressiveness required to represent this information leads to an extensibility which may allow future applications to increase in efficiency and gain a deeper understanding of the true preferences of an individual.

In order to correctly test our approach we take in in-depth look into one particularly well studied area that aims to apply a formal structure to an inherently subjective phenomenon: consonance, dissonance and roughness. This topic provides a great deal of related work. Data gathered from various studies provide a strong benchmark to which we can compare our own results.

We aim for our approach to be applicable to many domains. Even though the phenomenon of consonance, dissonance and roughness varies across cultures, it is globally understood as a core quality of musical experience. This makes it a topic that we may all have a fair opinion of — subjective as it may be — regardless of expertise.

1.2 Layout of Paper

This paper covers three main areas: the background to our test-bed, our implementation and experiment, and finally, our discussion and conclusions.

The background to our test-bed is described in section 2. In this section we introduce the concepts of consonance, dissonance and roughness followed by an outline of a number of studies carried out on the topic in relation to pairs of musical notes played in harmony (dyads). The studies described have all attempted to develop knowledge in an area that is subjective, culturally influenced and prone to inconsistencies from an individual perspective and across a population. We continue the section with a review of these studies. Section 3 describes in detail the specific challenges we face in designing our approach, based on our review in section 2.3.

Our implementation and experimentation is described in sections 4 and 5.

Finally, our discussion in section 6 provides some context for our results and contains some possible future work and improvements to our current approach, followed by our conclusions in section 7.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1 Consonance, Dissonance and Roughness

Consonance and dissonance, a notion of pleasant or unpleasant harmonies respectively, are fundamental to our understanding of musical aesthetics. The concept is greatly influenced by cultural differences and is largely subjective across individuals. It is also largely influenced by timbre which varies between sound sources and may introduce beatings between close harmonics. This makes it difficult to build a strong representational model of consonance or dissonance that holds across cultures and over time.

Since Pythagoras, consonance has been observed to correlate to the frequency ratios of notes. Galileo was the first to draw the connection between these ratios and the operation of the eardrum. He noted that pairs of musical notes with simple integer frequency ratios tended to sound more pleasant than those with more complex ratios, with the eardrum “kept in perpetual torment” [9].

The idea of “roughness” was first introduced by Helmholtz [10] to describe the auditory phenomenon of harsh sounding signals due to amplitude fluctuations or a “beating” ef-

fect. It has been hypothesised that the roughness of a signal has a strong equivalence to the consonance or dissonance of that signal, at least within western music, however, the link between this measure and some notion of aesthetics is unclear [11–13].

2.2 Previous Studies

There have been numerous approaches to modelling the consonance or roughness of musical intervals both mathematically and experimentally based on trials involving human subjects.

Helmholtz, wrote at length about the topic of roughness [10]. His observations, though often referenced and strikingly similar to more modern revisions, were not much more than personal observations based on musical theory. However his model of roughness provided a starting point for further research to expand upon.

Malmberg published a study which tested 1045 subjects in three distinct groups between 1913 and 1915 for their preferences of consonance [14]. Subjects were played two pairs of tones – dyads, “or two-clangs” in Malmberg’s words – on a piano or violin and asked to select which they preferred in terms of consonance. A strong effort was made to ensure all subjects understood the concept of consonance as Malmberg noted “the fundamental reason for the great divergence in the ranking by experts and the consequent disparagement of the ranking of consonance and dissonance has been due to the failure to take common ground in the definition of these terms”.

Malmberg’s study was conducted on a scale that has not since been reproduced. However, he did not build a ranking solely based on the responses of his subjects. Malmberg’s tests aimed to compare the responses of his 1045 subjects – the “empirical ranking” – to a “norm”, a ranking which had been developed based on the responses of “eight observers [who] were carefully selected on the basis of their training and fitness for the work”. The eight observers were originally required to produce independent rankings, of which the averages would become the “norm”, however Malmberg notes that after an initial conference, the “discussion and mutual criticism was so stimulating and interesting that all the observers agreed to sit again and continue by the same method until all should agree and a unanimous verdict could be handed in as in the case of a jury”. The results of this study appear unprincipled and highlight potential difficulties in obtaining agreement in this domain.

Though the results obtained from Malmberg’s observers did not directly affect the responses of his empirical study, the order of presentation and the particular dyads compared by subjects were based on his initial flawed study which may have affected his final results.

Plomp and Levelt described their approach to investigating the effect of critical bandwidth — the sensory limitations of hearing — on consonance by having subjects rate pairs of tones (generated by sine-wave oscillators) on a seven point scale, consonant to dissonant [1] with 1 corresponding to most dissonant, 7 corresponding to most consonant. They mention that some subjects had to ask for a

definition of “consonant” which they provided as “beautiful and euphonious” as it had been ascertained that “consonant, beautiful and euphonious are highly correlated for naive subjects.” Obviously Plomp and Levelt conducted these experiments with a relationship between consonance and aesthetics in mind, which serves to highlight a point made by Malmberg regarding a failure to adopt a common ground on the definition of consonance and dissonance leading to disagreement in the domain.

Though the experimental set up that Plomp and Levelt used was rather inelegant — equipment had to be readjusted by hand between each test — their tests have a number of aspects in common with future studies. Firstly, as mentioned above the subjects in their tests were not all musically trained. Secondly, the tone pairs, generated for their tests were composed of simple sine waves which reduced the tonal complexity of the resulting sound presented to the subject. Finally, their subjects rated tone pairs on a graduated scale.

Plomp and Levelt generated tone pairs about a set of mean frequencies (125, 250, 500, 1000 and 2000 Hz) and used a separate sample group for each. The sample groups were reduced in size from 19, 22, 18, 11 and 18 to 11, 10, 11, 10 and 8 respectively when they removed subjects who displayed incoherent responses.

Kameoka and Kuriyagawa conducted an independent study on the absolute and relative consonance of dyads [12]. Like Plomp and Levelt, their sample groups included two groups and their sample tones were generated using sine-wave oscillators, similar to [1]. In contrast however, subjects were not asked to rank consonance and dissonance absolutely (as in [1]) but rather in a relative manner. Subjects were presented with two dyads (A and B) and asked to provide an answer on a five point scale, -2, -1, 0, 1, or 2 “according to the subjective distance in consonance between A and B. If B is more consonant than A, a plus sign and if more dissonant, a minus sign was given” [12].

The groups chosen by Kameoka and Kuriyagawa for their experiments are rather puzzling. The first, “audio engineers, who are regarded as ordinary people” and the other, “mixers of ... the Japan Broadcasting Corporation”, later referred to as “specialists” [12]. It should be obvious to any reader that a person working in the field of audio engineering is far from an ordinary person in the context of their perception of musical consonance and dissonance. The authors proceed to mention that their “experiments were carried out with audio engineers, and the results in this paper should be interpreted as for ordinary people”, a contradiction in itself.

It should be noted that Kameoka and Kuriyagawa used exclusively Japanese speaking subjects. This resulted in the concepts of consonance and dissonance being defined in an entirely different language, adding a further layer of complexity to Malmberg’s notion of the definitions of these concepts and how that may affect a subject’s response. Additionally, there may also have been a cultural influence which, as stated previously, may have a strong effect on a subject.

Hutchinson and Knopoff later produced a “formalism”

for calculating the consonance of a pair of notes based on the work of Helmholtz, Malmberg and Plomp and Levelt. [15]. In their paper they discuss a number of formulas which serve to produce absolute values of consonance for different intervals. The comparison of their values to the results produced by Malmberg seem to show a large degree of correlation, however they fail to provide a direct assessment of their values by means of experiment.

2.3 Issues with Previous Studies

It has been noted that there are issues with the reproducibility of both studies carried out by Kameoka and Kuriyagawa, and Hutchinson and Knopoff [16]. This would suggest that the methods they used were simply not informative enough to accurately describe the behaviour of their subjects.

Plomp and Levelt had their subjects rank note pairs in an absolute 7 point graduated scale [1]. Malmberg based his ranking on the unanimous decisions of hand picked experts and then tested on large groups of subjects all at once, with a common test pattern [14]. The work of Plomp and Levelt, and Malmberg has been the basis of other papers attempting to produce a formulation of consonance, such as Hutchinson and Vassilakis [15] [11]. None of these studies have taken into account the contextual effects of juxtaposing particular note pairs or ranking intervals absolutely and the effects these approaches may have on results.

For example, the first note pair a subject is presented with is the only pair that does not follow a previous pair and thus has no context. The subject knows the pair must fall somewhere on the scale of dissonance provided but without any reference point, their first response is arbitrary. Alternatively, if a subject is given a number of note pairs in succession which would otherwise have been ranked on one extreme of the scale, they may be more likely to spread their ranking across the scale. Furthermore, after these similarly ranked note pairs, if a new note pair is given that, in another context would be close to the center of the scale, the subject might subconsciously rank this pair further to the other extreme of the scale. It could be argued that successive dyads may be presented to subjects with a large enough interval to ensure short term memory does not effect the response. Indeed Plomp and Levelt adopted this strategy with a 4 second interval [1], however other studies do not follow this paradigm, for example Kameoka and Kuriyagawa who mention an interval of only 0.5 seconds [12].

The problem here is context. Human beings are heavily influenced by context which can lead to incoherent responses. Studies conducted like those described in this paper depend on each test being free from contextual influences from previous tests, which is simply not possible given the experiment design in the studies mentioned earlier.

There are three main solutions to this contextual conundrum. Firstly, to present pairwise comparisons rather than an absolute ranking which reduces the effect of a user subconsciously dispersing their rankings. This approach was adopted by Kameoka and Kuriyagawa with success [12]. Secondly, to test subjects individually and present comparisons in a random order, which will reduce the effect

that the first note pair presented without context has on the result across a population. Finally, some studies like [1] use test intervals in a training session to establish a relative scale for a subject. However there are issues with this approach as different studies may train subjects to different degrees, by different methods, or indeed over train subjects and introduce fatigue.

In many earlier studies this solution was not achievable. Malmberg went to great lengths to find reproducible tones, testing pianos, organs, violins and bottles filled with wax among other instruments. If the subjects had been tested individually, it would have been arduous on the musicians and unreliable in terms of producing identical note pairs due to the fluctuations in timbre and pitch over time due to fatigue and temperature or humidity changes. With modern computer systems, it is possible to produce identical tones over and over again, as well as randomizing test orders fairly and handling the resulting data.

Another problem we have seen is how researchers may simply disregard incoherent, or contradictory responses from subjects [1]. We believe there is information to be gathered from contradictory responses and that rather than being disregarded, contradictions may actually provide a greater insight into the subjective preferences of test subjects, whether it be consonance, dissonance, aesthetics or any other subjective – or noisy – domain. Once again, it may have been the technological constraints of the time that forced researchers to reduce the complexity of their analytical processes, but with modern technology it should be achievable to handle these cases.

2.4 Ranking Methods

The Copeland Score, or Copeland Method [7] is a very common and easily understood ranking method. Nodes are ranked by their out-degree, or alternatively their out-degree minus their in-degree. This method, while easily understood, often leads to ties and bears no relation to the overall structure of the graph. In our ranking approach we use this method to find or break ties.

Kameoka and Kuriyakawa asked their subjects to rank dyads on a scale between -2 and 2. These absolute rankings were then normalized across the population using a simple normalisation function described by Guilford [17].

Plomp and Levelt used a similar method of ranking dyads on an absolute scale but used a 7 point scale (1-7). The lower quartile, median, and upper quartile of subject responses were used as consonance values [1].

3. ISSUES FACED

It has been shown that the previous studies have not provided sufficient evidence to describe the preferences or behaviour of their subjects without question or doubt [16]. As we have seen, there are two main issues here: changing context, and subject incoherence. We propose a different method of ranking which allows subjects to make pairwise comparisons which removes contextual issues, and map those comparisons to a directed graph which allows

us to make use of otherwise incoherent or contradicting responses.

3.1 Changing Context

We propose tackling the problem of changing context by forcing a relative context upon subjects. Subjects should only compare two objects — as in Kameoka and Kuriyakawa [12] — rather than provide an absolute response (ie, grading objects on a scale) — as in Plomp and Levelt [1]. For example, rather than asking a subject to provide a value for objects A and B in succession, a subject is asked only to say which object, A or B, is more expressive of the value being tested. A subject might say that object A is more dissonant than object B. In this case, we now know that for whatever dissonance value we assign to object A, object B will always be less than or equal to that value. We refer to this as a *dominance* where A is dominant over B, or $A > B$.

The objects being tested, in this case A and B, can be represented as two nodes on a directed graph. A dominance is represented on the graph as an edge between two nodes. In the example above, we would produce a graph with two nodes, A and B, with an edge between them directed from A to B representing the dominance of A over B.

As currently described, the relationship between two objects A and B may have three possible values. A is dominant over B, B is dominant over A, or both A and B are dominant over each other. In this last case, we have a cycle.

This representation can be further expanded. If we extend the responses available to subjects to enable them to say how strong a dominance is (with a sliding scale perhaps), we can model a more expressive response. A more expressive response can be represented on a graph as a weight or distance associated with a directed edge.

3.2 Subject Incoherence

Incoherence refers to a subject contradicting their previous responses. As a subject becomes familiar with the boundaries of the experiment they may express more coherent responses. In our approach, we assume incoherence is affected mainly by two factors: familiarity with the experiment and fatigue over time. We have mentioned that in some studies the responses from incoherent subjects were disregarded. We believe that this is a failure of the data collection method. We now outline our approach to minimizing the introduction of incoherence, and handling incoherence that may be introduced.

To minimize the influences that increase incoherence, we adopt the following approaches. Firstly, regarding familiarity with the experiment, a subject's first responses may not be as accurate as their later responses. This effect is partly addressed by pairwise comparison, but further reduced across a population by posing initial questions in a random order. Secondly, a subject will become inconsistent over time as fatigue and boredom begin to affect their attention. To this end, we allow subjects to stop at any point if they feel bored, tired or uncomfortable. In this case we can still provide a partial ranking due to the initial random distribution of dominances throughout the graph (see 4.1).

On a graph, incoherence and contradiction manifests as a cycle. On a graph without weighting, a cycle implies a tie between all of the nodes on the cycle, where each node in the cycle is equal in value. In this way, we can now handle incoherences safely, without losing information about unrelated coherent responses.

It may also be possible to represent contradicting responses as a cycle while producing a fully ranked result by using a weighted graph. This is discussed further in 6.3.

4. APPLICATION OF THE DIGRAPH

It would be beyond the scope of this article to describe the entire implementation of our approach. However, in the following section we will briefly introduce the core concepts of our implementation for the purpose of clarity and to justify the data we have obtained.

Briefly, we generate a digraph for each subject based on their preferences. The objects we wish to rank — in this case musical intervals — are represented by nodes, and questions posed to the subject are represented by edges on the graph. The purpose of ranking a digraph is to produce a list of nodes in a ranked order. Maximally efficient ranking will produce a fully ranked list (ie. no nodes with the same ranking) with the minimum number of edges. Individual rankings may then be simply normalised by calculating the average rank of a node across the population.

By using this structure we should be able to begin with a totally unconnected graph and ask questions to the subject one by one until: **a)** we have a fully ranked list, **b)** the subject becomes fatigued and wishes to stop, or **c)** we have asked some arbitrary number of questions to prevent subjects from becoming fatigued.

To implement this approach we must provide mechanisms to answer the following questions:

- How do we decide which edges to add and in what order?
- How do we define the ranking of objects, given some set of edges?

4.1 Adding Edges

To add edges to the graph we calculate a rank for each node on the graph (see 4.2), and proceed by breaking the ties between equally ranked nodes by adding an additional edge between them — *ie.* by asking a question of the subject to rank two nodes. Nodes that are explicitly tied — part of a cycle — are not considered in this process.

In the case where we have no more ties to break, we can either finish questioning the subject or over-sample (see section 6.2) by using a different method of calculating ties, such as the Copeland score method [7].

4.2 Ranking Nodes

The ranking of nodes provides a mechanism to both calculate ties in order to add more edges, and output a ranked list for a subject when testing is complete. The ranking algorithm used to calculate the final rank of nodes in a digraph must obviously remain constant across a population.

Figure 1. A sample graph and rankings. δ_B^f shows the forward nodes reachable from B.

Due to the possibility of some digraphs across a population being sparse, the ranking algorithm must accommodate for this.

The particular ranking algorithm used is not important. Although there are a number of algorithms designed to sort directed acyclic graphs [3], we are not aware of any formally defined algorithms that suit our specific needs by allowing cycles and ties. We therefore introduce our own ranking algorithm.

Though this un-weighted graph provides a limited expressiveness, Figure 3 shows that the use of this graph can provide a strong representation of the ranking of objects, especially when normalized across a population of test subjects. In section 6.3 we discuss the application of a weighted graph which may be more expressive.

Given the set of forward nodes reachable from a node n as δ_n^f , the rank $R(n) = |\delta_n^f| + 1$, as demonstrated in Figure 1. In this way we ensure that $R(n_1) \geq R(n_2)$ where $n_1 \succ n_2$. Calculating the rank in this way also means that nodes in a cycle will have an equal ranking, as they will all be reachable from each other.

The above ranking method can be calculated trivially for any node using a depth first search.

5. EXPERIMENT

We now describe an experiment conducted to show the effective implementation of the algorithm described in section 4. A small sample group of 25 subjects were presented with the experiment using recordings of piano notes to dynamically produce dyads. Dyads were produced using notes across two octaves, from A4 (440 Hz) to A6 (1760 Hz). Only intervals from 1 to 11 semitones were tested — unison and octave dyads were excluded to avoid confusion. The single sample group included both musicians and non-musicians, males and females, aged 21 to 57. All subjects were brought up within the western music culture.

Figure 2. A screen shot of the testing software. Users were asked to click on the red sound icons and select the appropriate pair using the buttons below.

5.1 Method

Each subject was tested separately. Subjects were first presented with a guideline document which described the testing software, the format of the experiment and the definition of consonance as: “Agreement or compatibility between opinions or actions”, and further: “When two tones tend to blend or fuse and produce a relatively smooth and pure resulting sound, they are said to be consonant”. This second definition is based on the description by Malmberg [14].

Each subject was then presented with the software as shown in Figure 2. Dyads — described as “pairs” to subjects — were played by clicking sound icons at the top of the screen, and a preference was defined by clicking the appropriate buttons below. After each preference selection, a screen with the words “Click to Continue” was displayed in order to prevent accidental preference selection.

Each preference was presented in order to break ties as describe in 4.1. Testing finished when all ties had been broken and a full ranking was achieved.

5.2 Results

Subjects provided an average of 24.8 preferences before a full ranking could be calculated and completed the test in an average of approximately 6 minutes. This is in contrast to the minimum of 55 potential preferences required with a semi-complete graph with 11 nodes (V), given as: $\frac{V^2-V}{2}$. The sample mean ranking of each interval is shown in Figure 3. This ranking is compared to previous data — we use Hutchinson and Knopoff [15], and Malmberg as examples [14] — as shown in Figure 4 and Table 1, also see [11, 12] for other comparable results. It can be seen that our ranking follows a similar pattern to previous data where the intervals of 1 and 11 semitones tend to be less consonant (more dissonant, rough) and the interval of 6 semitones is conspicuously lower than its highly ranked neighbours of 5 and 7 semitones.

Figure 3. The mean ranking of intervals across a population of size 25 using an un-weighted digraph. Error bars show standard error of the mean.

	Correlation Coefficient	P-value
Hutchinson & Knopoff	0.788	0.004
Malmberg	0.852	0.001

Table 1. Correlation of digraph rankings with previous studies.

6. DISCUSSION

Though our experiment was carried out on a relatively small sample size, our results show a strong resemblance and correlation to previous studies. Even with a simple un-weighted graph and no questions asked beyond those necessary to break all ties.

6.1 Experimental Improvements

Along with a larger sample size, a number of other improvements could be made to the experiment. Primarily, we conducted the experiment using piano notes which contain many harmonics. In-harmonic frequencies in the piano notes may have had an affect on the results produced. Piano notes were selected rather than pure sinusoidal tones in order to compare our results to the largest previous study, carried out by Malmberg [14], which used piano notes. A future study could be conducted to compare our results to those obtained from previous studies using pure tones.

The experiment outlined in this paper can be seen as the simplest implementation of the ranking digraph. We intend to further explore the possibility of building a more expressive and efficient ranking process for subjective preferences. The following sections discuss these possibilities.

6.2 Over-sampling

Our current approach of calculating ties and asking questions to break those ties does not allow subjects to specify

Figure 4. Comparison of results to previously published rankings [14, 15].

cycles. Subjects may express cycles if given the opportunity and we feel this information may be an important factor in the ability of any graph to accurately reflect the preferences of an individual.

To improve our current approach and allow cycles to form we propose **over-sampling**: continuing to ask preferences even after all ties have been broken. As noted in section 4.1, a different method of ranking can be used to implement this and calculate new ties.

6.3 Graph Implementation Improvements: Weighted Graph

By using a weighted graph it may be possible to both allow cycles to form, and fully rank objects, even when cycles are present in the graph. To achieve this we propose the following potential solutions.

6.3.1 Handling Cycles

In an un-weighted graph, cycles of more than 2 nodes may form, leading to many nodes in an explicit tie. In the case of a weighted graph, where a weight $W \in \mathbb{N}$ and $0 < W < 1$, we make the assumption that in a tie, the edge with the lowest W can be safely excluded in order to break the tie and fully rank all nodes on a graph. In a cycle where there is no singular lowest W , we cannot break the tie and proceed with all nodes in the cycle tied, and of equal value.

This solution relies on the proper ranking of nodes within a sparse weighted digraph.

6.3.2 Ranking a Weighted Graph

The weighted graph may provide a deeper expressiveness at the expense of the simplicity of implementation. A number of ranking methods exist for weighted directed acyclic graphs [8, 18] however the vast majority of research in the area assumes semi-complete or complete graphs and will not handle cycles. We therefore outline our own algorithm as one possible approach to this challenge.

Given a digraph $D = (N, E)$, a subset N_x^f (forward neighbours of x , nodes that x points to), and a subset N_x^b (backward neighbours of x , nodes that point to x) we make use of a two pass approach as described below. A two pass approach is necessary to handle ranking imbalances which occur when nodes form disconnected branches, of differing weights, sharing a common root.

First pass

Populate the working set W with all end nodes (nodes with zero outgoing edges). For each node $n \in W$, move it to the visited set V , give it a ranking $R(n) = 1$ and add all nodes pointing to n , N_n^b to W . To iterate through the entire graph, for each node $n \in W$ with forward neighbours (N_n^f) such that $N_n^f \subseteq V$, calculate the rank of n as

$$R(n) = \sum_{i \in N_n^f} E_{i,n} i \quad (1)$$

where $E_{x,y}$ is the weight of the edge between nodes x and y . Continue until $|W| = 0$.

Second pass

$V = \emptyset$. Populate W with all start nodes (nodes with zero incoming edges). For each node $n \in W$, move it to V , keep its ranking the same as the first pass and add N_n^f to W . Iterate through to the entire graph, for each node $n \in W$ where $N_n^b \subseteq V$, calculate the rank of n as

$$R(n) = \sum_{i \in N_n^b} E_{i,n} i \quad (2)$$

Continue until $|W| = 0$.

7. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a detailed review of the literature in the area of the consonance, dissonance and roughness of dyads concerning our test bed. We outline some of the shortcomings of these studies and our findings based on this research provide the basis for the design of our ranking system.

We have identified an algorithmic approach to handling subjective preferences using a graph that can efficiently rank objects, express contradictory responses from subjects and provide a basis for extending this approach.

Our test bed experiment produced a ranking of objects within a subjective domain using a small sample group. We did so with a much smaller set of questions per subject than previous studies [12, 14, 15], in a way that minimized the effect of contextual issues and subject incoherence found in previous studies.

Finally, we have also proposed possible methods of extending our approach using over sampling and ranking subject responses using a more expressive weighted graph.

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